

Discussion on the new CMIP6-Baseline runs

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**Complete the protocol phase 3 (available online)
in order to establish a FINAL common protocol to
be followed by all the participants (facilitating
also the intercomparison among the projections)**

- Follow the CORDEX protocol for CMIP6 simulations : for experiments and data request
- https://cordex.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/CORDEX-CMIP6_exp_design
- <https://cordex.org/experiment-guidelines/cordex-cmip6/data-request>
- Absolutely needed for multi-model comparisons

Base 3 protocol : mandatory elements?

Consensus

- Med-CORDEX domain
- Atm model (minimum) resolution: 0.11° or 12 km
- Ocean model (minimum) resolution: $1/12^\circ$ or 10 km
- River coupling from land to ocean
- Evaluation simulation using ERA5 (ATM)/ORAS5(OCE)
- Scenario choice : SSP370, SSP126
- Period : (minimum) 1979-2020 for eval, (1960-2100) for scenario
- Nile : (at least) a common seasonal cycle (same as in phase 2)

Base 3 protocol : mandatory elements?

After discussion (1)

- Coupling frequency : at least 1h for atm-oce, 1day for river-ocean
- LBC : GCM choice for historical scenario (cf. S. Somot talk)
 - Selection of the GCM following 4 families of criteria (data availability, plausibility, future diversity, GCM independence)
 - Discussion still opened for the choice between all groups
- A common bathymetry : try to use the same original database
- Spin-up strategy (cf. G. Jordà talk)
 - 2 possible choices : run the model on a long period (cycle forcing or random years), or on a short period
 - Must be based on observations and acceptable uncertainties on the trends
 - Work in progress with a box model method
- Ocean ICs: can we share the same ? MedHYMAPv2.2 ? (see G. Jordà)
 - The spin-up strategy might change a lot the ocean state
 - MedHYMAP is the reference for most of the groups

Base 3 protocol : mandatory elements?

After discussion (2)

- Aerosols : at least a static dataset for eval
 - Importance of evolving dataset, with a trend in the past
 - Example of reanalysis dataset : MERRA-2
- Sea level (cf. G. Sannino talk, example of set-up in Sannino et al., 2021)
 - Zos variable as output of the model
 - In evaluation simulations, all the global components (ice melting, thermosteric, dynamic...) are included in the forcing data (usually satellite)
 - In historical and scenario simulations, the global average thermosteric variable must be added a posteriori
- Black Sea : simple parameterization? What about Temp and Sal?
 - When the Black Sea is not included in the ocean model, a solution is to input the Black Sea inflow as a river in the Aegean Sea, with its E-P-R budget (E-P from the atm model, R from the river model)
- A complete description of the coupled system set-up :
 - A table on the Med-CORDEX website with each key-element as a column, each coupled system as a line

Base 3 protocol : recommended elements

- Ocean lateral boundary condition :
 - See the mandatory elements slide for the GCM choice
 - Use a bias correction approach if the GCM shows significant biases with respect to ORAS5 reanalysis for temperature and salinity (difference between reanalysis and GCM as correction)
 - Try to use the same as the other groups for the same GCM forcing
- Aerosols : a realistic dataset for evaluation run
- GHG : realistic for past runs, see P. Nabat if needed
- Chlorophyll- : surface climatology (contact R. Pennel) or on-line biogeochemistry model
- A river routing scheme
- Other point ?

Outputs of the simulations

Mandatory :

1. Lists of variables available for atm, river, aerosol, to be finished for ocean (Hurry up Sam:D)
 - Available on zenodo.org/communities/medcordex
2. File naming : follow CMIP6-CORDEX, CF-CMOR netcdf format

After discussion :

3. Data sharing ENEA MedCORDEX database for beginning or ESGF ?
 - Agreement of ENEA for a small list of variables to allow the validation of the models
 - ESGF for the complete output

Documentation

- Articles (white papers for the Mediterranean region?)
- Protocol to be updated on zenodo
 - cf. zenodo.org/communities/medcordex